

LOCAL STRATEGIES FOR INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE PRESERVATION IN DISPLACED NIGERIAN COMMUNITIES

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The preservation of indigenous knowledge in Nigeria is increasingly threatened particularly in communities where displacement and environmental change pose increasing challenges to the preservation of Indigenous Knowledge (IK) in Nigeria. This challenge is notably prominent in the Northeast's conflict-affected areas. This study looks at the long-standing issues that indigenous communities and the official preservation sector face while working together, such as mistrust, the perception of Western dominance, and the psychological gap that exists between indigenous communities and urban preservation agents. The study highlights particular challenges like underfunded preservation policies, cultural disruptions brought on by migration, and the decline of oral traditions through critical analysis and field-based reflections. The authors suggest three locally grounded strategies for preserving Indigenous Knowledge- the resuscitation of storytelling culture for digitization, the establishment of secure spaces for recording lived experiences, and the development of local communities of practice (CoPs) as a long-term model for knowledge sharing.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria today, very few communities can boast of a well organised local or formal preservation system of indigenous knowledge or practices. It is equally not an exaggeration to submit that in all of the 36 States of Nigeria, there is a common problem

of a rapid decline in preservation of cultural practices and indigenous knowledge. This issue is in dire need of attention in communities that are displaced or on the verge of being displaced due to the Boko Haram conflict and the current climate change in Northern Nigeria. As a phenomenon deeply rooted in culture and unique to the people belonging to that particular culture, Indigenous Knowledge has been left alone to oral transmission. According to the World Bank in 2009, it was stated that the corpus of indigenous knowledge and skills that are embedded in a society's culture are unique to it and therefore constitutes its indigenous Knowledge [1]. However, the transmission of these knowledge heavily depends on the willingness and desire of the Indigenous knowledge holders and the upcoming generation of youths widely considered as leaders of tomorrow to prioritise these preservations and sustainability of cultural practices.

This paper attempts to propose strategies that will reinforce a collaboration between digital preservation community and the indigenous communities in the preservation of Indigenous Knowledge. Emphasis will be made on allowing indigenous communities ownership of the process. The suggestions are reflective of communities that are considered as more vulnerable.

II. CHALLENGES OF PRESERVING INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE

The global challenge of preservation in the 21st Century differs across regions of the world. In the context of Nigeria, the challenge of preservation are numerous. Chief amongst these challenges which in our opinion has been underemphasised is the psychological aspect. Because urban dwellers are closer to Western cultures and education, this has created a gap between them and indigenous knowledge communities. As researchers, this sometimes creates a challenge of acceptance during field research. There is also a general lack of awareness about the immediate and future significance of preservation and the consequences of its neglect. This fuels apathy, making it difficult to mobilize community-driven initiatives [2]. Also, field experience with indigenous communities has shown that majority of them nurse the belief that the differences between urban and indigenous local communities transcends beyond differences in lifestyle. They hold the belief that a collaboration on anything may not be possible. This paper is an attempt to bridge this gap in thinking and perception strategically through a sustainable collaboration and networking between indigenous local communities and digital preservation community.

In addition, the following are challenges within displaced communities in Nigeria which further necessitates local strategies of preservation that reflects the realities of local indigenous communities.

Delay in coming up with a robust preservation policy: The ongoing underfunding of preservation activities and organizations is a serious problem since it impairs their ability to carry out efficient implementation [2]. Systemic corruption and poor management, which frequently result in the illegal trafficking of cultural artifacts and the degradation of heritage sites, exacerbate this issue [3].

Conflict in local communities: The preservation of Indigenous Knowledge (IK) systems in Nigeria is seriously threatened by the uprooting of communities caused by conflict and climate change. Whole communities have been uprooted from their ancestral lands in areas like the Northeast, where Boko Haram's insurgency has caused widespread displacement. This has disrupted the intergenerational transmission of knowledge ingrained in daily routines, rituals, and interactions with the land [4]. Indigenous Knowledge in these contexts, from farming systems and cosmological

beliefs to medicinal practices and oral traditions is closely linked to place, and its loss during displacement disrupts resilience strategies that have historically allowed communities to withstand environmental shocks in addition to affecting cultural identity [5, 6].

Deaths and migration of holders of these IK and practices: Despite its effectiveness, oral preservation of IK and cultural memory carries some risks. Indigenous knowledge is particularly vulnerable when displaced populations are relocated to unfamiliar rural or urban settings where formal education systems and dominant cultures frequently take precedence due to its informal nature, which is frequently transmitted orally or embodied in communal rituals. The risk requires documentation using a number of methods. Both tangible and intangible legacy are now under much greater risk due to rapid urbanization and environmental degradation, especially deforestation and unchecked infrastructure expansion [7]. Furthermore, cultural icons, including UNESCO-recognized sites like the Osun-Osogbo Sacred Grove, are under serious risk due to climate change-related phenomena like erosion and floods [8].

Disconnect between local communities and formal preservation bodies: Even though the importance of indigenous knowledge systems is well acknowledged, Western epistemologies and bureaucratic structures continue to significantly influence preservation frameworks, frequently excluding or marginalizing local perspectives [9]. This misalignment leads to top-down, culturally insensitive preservation efforts that are occasionally viewed as extractive or even intrusive by the populations they are intended to save [15]. Ndoro and Chirikure in their 2008 study, indigenous people are frequently viewed as stakeholders rather as co-creators or legacy guardians, which diminishes their agency and upholds historical power disparities [16].

III. LOCAL STRATEGIES FOR PRESERVING IK AND PRACTICES

These strategies are informed through the reflections of the authors experiences, interactions with indigenous communities and understanding of the terrain from an insiders point of view.

Re-enacting/Reviving the story telling culture for digitisation: Already established in previous study is the understanding that despite the richness of indigenous knowledge systems that could inform sustainable preservation, Indigenous Knowledge is

frequently overlooked in favor of Western approaches, leading to culturally disconnected strategies [6] (KNBBS, 2023). Therefore, to mitigate this problem, the authors suggest a revival of the storytelling culture. These stories can further be digitised (Digital storytelling) in such a way that both parties have access and ownership of the material. This strategy reflects the disruption of traditional, institution-led archival models and recognizing the storytelling practices of indigenous communities as legitimate, dynamic, and worthy of digital translation. It challenges dominant knowledge hierarchies and embraces a culturally grounded form of innovation in preservation.

Creating a Safe Space for Documenting people's experiences: In traditional preservation strategies, the everyday experiences and oral histories of local people are frequently neglected in favor of material culture and institutional narratives [9]. Indigenous communities are conservative, so it is essential to establish a secure and welcoming environment for recording their lived experiences. Especially in communities impacted by trauma, marginalization, or displacement, this will be an essential part of moral and sustainable preservation. Additionally, the survival of indigenous knowledge systems and intangible cultural assets depends heavily on personal narratives. However, preservation initiatives must deliberately establish safe, trusting environments where people feel heard, respected, and in control of how their memories are captured, understood, and shared if they are to produce meaningful and non-extractive documentation [10].

Informed permission must be obtained, power dynamics must be addressed, culturally relevant techniques (such as performance, visual arts, or oral testimony) must be used, and contributors' rights to access, own, or limit their contributions must be upheld [11]. In order to create these safe spaces, it is also necessary to use indigenous languages, train community-based facilitators, and protect emotional health, particularly in environments that have experienced trauma or violence [12]. When handled with tact, these methods not only help communities retain their knowledge but also provide them the freedom to create their own legacy however they see fit. This strategy challenges extractive documentation practices by introducing culturally sensitive, participant-led preservation. It redefines ethical engagement, shifting the preservation

encounter into a dialogical, emotionally aware space that honors indigenous agency and reimagines how memory and trauma are handled in heritage work.

Building a Sustainable local Community of Practice: In Northeast Nigeria, where indigenous communities have been severely impacted by long-term conflict, displacement, and climate-related disruptions, establishing local communities of practice (CoPs) provides a resilient and culturally grounded method of preserving Indigenous Knowledge (IK). Elders, young people, farmers, artisans, and traditional leaders can all gather in safe, cooperative settings through a CoP to exchange, record, and disseminate indigenous knowledge derived from their surroundings, social structures, and belief systems [13]. Additionally, by involving marginalized groups as active agents rather than passive beneficiaries in preservation processes, CoPs can empower marginalized groups, particularly women and youth [14]. CoPs in Northeast Nigeria can also help integrate traditional knowledge with contemporary environmental and educational strategies when backed by NGOs, local universities, and digital storytelling platforms. This will support cultural survival and sustainable development in a fragile ecological and sociopolitical landscape. This approach fosters inclusive spaces where traditional and modern preservation methods intersect. It subverts top-down models and encourages the co-creation of knowledge across generational, disciplinary, and cultural boundaries reimagining who leads, participates in, and benefits from preservation work.

IV. CONCLUSION

In Nigeria, indigenous knowledge preservation calls for immediate, inclusive, and context-sensitive measures, particularly in Northeastern communities that are experiencing displacement and cultural disintegration. The gaps that now exist between formal preservation agents and indigenous people are psychological, historical, and structural in nature. They are based on mistrust and epistemic exclusion. A change from top-down preservation frameworks to participatory ones that respect indigenous perspectives and traditions is necessary to overcome these obstacles. Preservation initiatives can gain greater significance and influence by revitalizing storytelling customs online, creating secure areas for genuine community involvement, and creating long-lasting local communities of practice. These

strategies not only safeguard indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage but also strengthen community resilience, foster intergenerational continuity, and ensure that indigenous communities are not passive subjects of preservation, but active creators and curators of their knowledge systems.

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